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Axiological approach to prevention of deviant behavior of blind students

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Abstract

The article substantiates the significance of value orientations of an individual with special educational needs in the aspect of prevention of deviant behavior. It is emphasized that there are practically no studies on the specifics of the value orientations of blind children as a factor determining their behavior. This article presents the results of the theoretical substantiation and survey, focused on the prevention of deviant behavior, (the author's method of L. P. Girfanova, aimed at identifying the attitude of children to universal values) of 10-11th grade students of the Ufa Correctional Boarding School No. 28 for blind and visually impaired students. It is shown that it is necessary to introduce such an element of prevention as value orientations of individuals that underlie their motivation of behavior. The value characteristics of the individual acquire special relevance in the conditions of increasing threats to life and health that have developed in the modern world due to the fact that there is a natural connection between the stability of the individuals' value orientations and the economic, socio-political and spiritual life of society. The practical significance of the research lies in understanding of the key role of the axiological approach in public prevention and social education of this category of children, providing them with "a worthy social position" in the system of public relations, as well as understanding of the essence of prevention as the formation of the value orientations stability and normative behavior of the individual.

Keywords: axiological approach, deviant behavior, prevention, problem field of prevention, directions and targets of prevention, value orientations, special educational needs.

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Introduction

Problems of prevention belong to interdisciplinary problems. In the pedagogical aspect, these are problems of:

- the lack of a common understanding of the phenomenon of "prevention" in the scientific literature, as well as the definition of its role and place in the terminological apparatus of pedagogical science, etc.;
- different understanding of the prevention problems, which consists of expanding pedagogical knowledge about its content (the subject field of "prevention") and its organization;
- the specifics of the organization of preventive activities for students with special educational needs.

In our opinion, the approach to prevention which consists of finding the causes of deviance, and then eliminating them or minimizing the root causes deserves the attention of researchers. However, it cannot be the only basis of preventive activity and be limited to this. It seems that the variable-subject approach developed by Kovalchuk (2002), which considers prevention as a two-way interrelated process, is the closest to the idea of prevention, due to the fact that the causal aspect is considered in conjunction with the allocated protection factor, defined as the development of the existential sphere. In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to introduce such an element of prevention as the individuals' value orientations that underlie their motivation of behavior, and further develop its content from the point of the stability of the person with special educational needs. We believe that the use of the axiological approach to the prevention of deviant behavior as a factor determining the behavior of students with special educational needs is extremely relevant.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to provide a theoretical substantiation and examine the value orientations of a person with special educational needs (the blind and visually impaired students) with the focus on the prevention of deviant behavior. The analysis of the problem showed that prevention is primarily based on the idea of identifying and eliminating factors of deviant behavior. The objectives of the study on the problems of prevention of deviant behavior, in our opinion, are to study them at two levels: scientific-pedagogical and professional-pedagogical (Syтина, Khabibova, & Girfanova, 2019). The concept of stability of value orientations is defined by us as the ability of a person to resist forces (threats) that seek to bring him or her out of balance and to compensate for the action of these forces.

This expressed in the state (i.e., the dominant way of his or her being), in which the person most fully ensures (self-realization) the realization of his or her capabilities as a principle of life activity (Khabibova, 2010).

Literature review

The analysis of scientific researches on the problem of prevention of deviant behavior of students with special educational needs allowed us to identify the following areas of research:

- problems of various aspects of the value orientations;
- problems of deviant behavior;
- problems of prevention of deviant behavior.

A significant number of researchers developed particular and general questions of the theory of values (axiology) (Anisimov, 1988; Tugarinov, 1966; Brozhik, 1982).

Many researchers consider the phenomenon of value orientations, its nature, main functions, and the process of formation (Leontiev, 1996; Gudechek, 1989; Momov, 1975).

In the English-language foreign literature values in education were considered by Barth (1994), Tomlinson (1995).

The problem of deviant behavior is developed at the intersection of various sciences: philosophical, sociological, pedagogical, socio-psychological, cultural, which, accordingly, have specific approaches to its consideration and justification.

Deviantology as an integrating science that studies social deviations (deviance) and the reaction of society to them (social control), according to Gilinsky (2007) and Hagurov (2003).

Pedagogical and psychological studies of deviation, including the problems of re-education, psychological and pedagogical work with adolescents with deviant behavior, were developed in the works of domestic scientists (Belicheva, 2009; Kleiberg, 2018).

In the problems of prevention, it is necessary to highlight the approaches to the organization of prevention:

- activity approach in the socio-pedagogical study of the prevention of deviations (Arlamov, 2012);

- environmental approach to the organization of the preventive process (Belicheva, 2009; Kleiberg, 2018);
- clinical and biological approach in preventive work (Derecha & Karpets, 2021);
- a variable-subject approach in preventive work (Kovalchuk, 2002).

Our own studies of the value orientations of children of the "risk group" have shown their undoubted relationship with the behavior of the individual (Girfanova, 2007; Khabibova & Kokin, 2008).

The analysis of the problem showed that prevention is primarily based on the idea of identifying and eliminating factors of antisocial behavior. And the algorithm of the prevention process can be presented as follows: first, the identification of a set of asocial causes and factors in the behavior of the individual in order to determine the directions of preventive actions and the choice of means, as well as the forms and methods of their implementation; second, the elimination or minimization of the identified root causes (Gilinsky, 2007).

Psychologists have identified a number of features of the personal behavior of visually impaired and blind children. We believe that a comparative analysis of these behavioral characteristics and value preferences allows us to determine which value orientations were formed in this category of children under the influence of the defect and the environment and caused deviations in behavior. It is well known that the child's system of value orientations is the basis that motivates his or her behavior.

According to Vygotsky (2003), who refers to Buerklen and the school of Adler, blindness, which has an organic nature, gives an impetus to the processes of compensation, which in turn causes the emergence of a number of psychological features in a blind child, reconstructing a number of its functions for solving vital tasks. Innate causes act indirectly through the resulting decline in the child's "social position". The consequence of this is the restructuring of the entire social life of the child, his or her connections with other people, a change in his or her place in social life, which, undoubtedly, we note, affects both the formation of his or her value orientations and the nature of his or her behavior. In this regard, Vygotsky (2003) highlights the concept of "unity and integrity of the developing personality of the child", noting that the personality develops as "a single whole with special laws...".

At the First Congress on Therapeutic Pedagogy in Germany, Vygotsky (2003), who was speaking about the incorrect recognition of certain values, noted that the reason for this should be sought "not in an innate anomaly of the will, and not in certain perversions of individual functions, but in the fact that neither the environment nor he himself has brought up the recognition of these values".

The education and development of blind children is primarily aimed at overcoming the difficulties associated with the social consequences of blindness. And here it becomes extremely important to prevent the emergence of "feelings of inferiority" by means of education (Alfred Adler) through the formation of a positive "I-concept" and the acceptance of the value "Man", which is a system-forming component of the entire set of universal values (Girfanova, 2010).

It is interesting to note that the Adler school, while offering the technique of encouragement within the framework of therapeutic pedagogy, believes that its field covers everything that threatens a person with loss of courage (Vygotsky, 2003).

Our research has shown that the category of "Courage" as a value-quality occupies a fairly high place in the value hierarchy of modern visually impaired and blind children, as can be seen from the analysis of the students' value preferences, presented below.

Analyzing the characteristics of blind children, Vygotsky (2003) puts forward the idea that blindness is not only the absence of vision, but causes a profound restructuring of all the forces of the body and personality, causing new forces to come to life, being a source of revealing new abilities. Referring to Alfred Adler, Vygotsky (2003) argues that the defect becomes the driving force of a person's mental development, and if his or her activity is successful, then the blind child not only copes with the difficulties arising from the defect, but rises in his or her development to the new level of giftedness, creating from "low-value – super-value". Hence, we draw an important conclusion about the importance of the situation of success in creating a positive "I-concept" of a child with disabilities and adopting value orientations of universal sound.

On the other hand, where the conflict of the defect with the external environment leads to failure, we are faced with the destruction of the individual, with the denial of socially significant values, with deviant behavior. In this boundless range of success and failure, there is an inexhaustible variety of personal development and its value orientations.

Methodology

We used theoretical methods, namely structural and content analysis. The empirical methods were observation and survey (questionnaire, diagnostic conversation). The author's method of Girfanova (2007), consisting of four questionnaires, aimed at identifying the attitude of children to universal values, as well as a diagnostic table for determining the level of value orientations formation; the method of determining self-attitude by Pantileev (1993), the method of studying children with learning difficulties by Luskanova (1993).

On April 8, 2021, we conducted a study of the value orientations of 10-11 grade visually impaired and blind children of the Ufa Correctional Boarding School No. 28. A total of 16 people took part in the study: 8 visually impaired and 8 blind students. In this study, this age category was chosen, since this age (17-19 years old) young people already have a well-established worldview, a system of value orientations. The participation in the study was voluntary and the informed consent of parents of the students was obtained. The study of the value orientations of high school students was conducted by means of a survey of two groups. For the visually impaired, the questionnaires were printed out in enlarged font, for blind children, the questionnaires were printed out using Braille code. Students were offered four questionnaires, each of which provided a list of fourteen values - goals, values - means, values - norms and values - qualities, respectively. The students had to rank each of the four lists according to the degree of significance for them. At the same time, they could cross out the values that they considered as insignificant.

Results

The study found that, overall, all children performed relatively well with the task. At the same time, visually impaired children quite easily coped with the ranking of all fourteen values, while blind children already showed some "confusion" in values, repetitions, and insufficient differentiation of value concepts. It is felt that the value orientations of blind students have not yet fully formed, the children have not yet comprehended and self-determined in relation to many of the values. Blind students have a predominant spread of value preferences, reflecting the range of personal preferences. But, nevertheless, there are general trends of this category of children.

In the category of values-goals, 50% of the respondents among the visually impaired put the concept of "Life" in the first place, the value of "Health" (the so-called "vital" values) in the second place; among the social values-goals, the children prefer the values of "Freedom" and "Justice", placing them in 1-3 places. The concept of "Beauty" has the least value for them.

Among blind students, the difference in value preferences with the visually impaired is small. For them, "Life" and "Health" are also the most important, but in the third place they distinguish the concept of "Man" and this is correlated with the value-the norm of "Self-esteem". And this confirms the conclusions of the study of the deep personality structures of senior schoolchildren with visual impairments, made by Vilenskaya (1990), that the level of claims of this category of children is underestimated in comparison with normal-sighted children. At the same time, the combination of high self-esteem and a low level of pretension indicates that they are quite satisfied with the average level of development (Vilenskaya, 1990).

The concepts of "the Earth" were the least significant among the blind, with 50% of respondents not considering the Earth as a value at all, perhaps not fully realizing this category as a planet, as well as "Richness", although "Labour" as a value-means is at a fairly high place in the system of preferences of blind children: 75% of respondents placed this category in 2-5 places. "Beauty" for the blind, as well as for the visually impaired, does not matter much. There is no doubt that the formation of aesthetic feelings in the visually impaired and blind is difficult due to visual impairment, since this turns off the whole range of feelings that arise from the visual perception of beauty. And here the opinion of Kuznetsova (2003) is very significant, stating that the formation of aesthetic feelings in the blind is primarily connected with education, since the ability to aesthetic pleasure develops not so much in the sphere of contemplation as in the sphere of activity.

The biggest value in the category of value-means for both the visually impaired and the blind is "Family": 63% and 50% of respondents, respectively, put the family unambiguously in the first place. But it is interesting to note that 38% of blind children do not consider the family as a value at all. It can be assumed that these are children from dysfunctional families, where parents are not interested in the fate and health of the child, but this statement requires additional research.

Among the values-norms, visually impaired students prefer the value of "Friendship" most of all (75% of children were placed in 1-4 places), when among the values-qualities, "Taking care of their health" is most important for them (100% of 1-3 places). For the blind in this category, the most significant are "good health, cheerfulness" (50% put on the 1st place) and, as already noted, "self-esteem" (38% on the 1st place). Among the values-qualities, "Optimism" and "Courage" clearly come out in the first place, although such a quality as "Tolerance" is also very attractive for them. Among the personal values, several people specifically noted purposefulness, the ability to achieve their goals.

Although among the children there were representatives of six nationalities (Russians, Bashkirs, Tatars, Marian, Ukrainian, Chechen), they unequivocally deny national identity as a value (88%), the concepts of "Fatherland" and "Patriotism" are put in the last place, although this is less pronounced among the visually impaired. And there is something to think about. In the conditions of a boarding school, this problem clearly lies in the field of education.

Among other values, it is interesting to note that the guys are quite indifferent to "education" and deny such a value as "Religion".

Discussion

Almost 100 years ago, Vygotsky (2003) proposed to understand the problem of blindness as a socio-psychological problem, and there are three main means to its solution: public prevention, social education and social work of the blind, which currently should be understood as the inclusion of children in a broad socially significant activity, boldly taking them beyond the limited framework of boarding schools.

And in this regard, it is interesting to note that Vygotsky (2003) actually pre-empted the currently declared inclusive education by demanding the elimination of "isolated and disabled education for the blind" and the blurring of the line between special and normal schools, stating that "the education of a blind child should be organized as the education of a child capable of normal development".

Compensation for blindness is carried out through the development of speech and here there is a wide opportunity to achieve social value in full. The success of social education and prevention of deviations largely depends on what socially significant personal qualities will be formed in children with visual impairments by the beginning of their independent life. And quite correctly, Solntseva & Deniskina (2004) note that this should be an integral system of personal relations, including:

- ideas about yourself, attitude to your defect, attitude to other people;
- attitude to life goals, to the past and future, to life values;
- attitude to the immediate social environment, relations with the other sex. And these relationships are the basic structure of the personality (Kuznetsova, 2003).

Conclusion

The practical significance of the research is to develop an axiologically oriented understanding of the essence of prevention as the formation of the value orientations stability and as a consequence, the stability of the normative behavior of the individual is proposed. In our opinion, the axiological approach should play a key role in public prevention and social education of children with special educational needs, providing them with a "worthy social position" in the system of public relations.

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